

ethanol (25 ml) was refluxed on a steam bath for about 6-7 hours. The reaction mixture acquired orange colour and an orange-brown solid separated, which was filtered, washed with 5% sodium bicarbonate solution and finally with water. The compound was purified by dissolving in sodium carbonate solution and then reprecipitating with acetic acid, m.p. $>290^\circ$, yield 0.6 g (44%), $\nu_{\max}$ (cm^{-1}) 1710, 1650, 1600, 1530, 1150, 755. (Found: S, 11.34; N, 20.46. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_6\text{N}_4\text{SO}_2$, S, 11.85; N, 20.74%).

2-Methyl-2, 3-dihydro-imidazo[2'. 1' : 2, 3]thiazolo [4,5-b]quinoxaline(III) :

A solution of I (1.00 g, 0.005 mole) and 4-methyl-2-mercapto imidazoline (0.58 g, 0.005 mole) in absolute ethanol (25 ml) was heated on a steam bath for about 5 hours. The yellow coloured solid thus obtained was filtered, washed with sodium bicarbonate solution and then with water. Crystallization from DMF afforded yellow micro-needles, m.p. $>300^\circ$, yield 0.4 g (33%), $\nu_{\max}$ (cm^{-1}) 1610, 1555, 1335, 1260, 1120, 755. (Found: S, 12.92. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{10}\text{N}_4\text{S}$, S, 13.22%).

2-Thio-thiazolo[4,5-b]quinoxaline(IV, R = H) :

It was prepared by refluxing a solution of I (1.0 g, 0.005 mole), ammonium dithiocarbamate (0.55 g, 0.005 mole), and anhydrous sodium acetate (0.82 g) in absolute ethanol (30 ml) for 3 hours. The yellow coloured solid was filtered, washed with water and crystallized from DMF m.p. $>300^\circ$, yield 0.7 g (64%), $\nu_{\max}$ (cm^{-1}) 3170, 3090, 1615, 1570, 1150, 835, 740. (Found: S, 28.84. Calcd. for $\text{C}_9\text{H}_8\text{N}_2\text{S}_2$, S, 29.22%). Similarly were prepared IV(R = o-HO-C₆H₄), m.p. $>290^\circ$, $\nu_{\max}$ (cm^{-1}) 3170-3040, 1610, 1555, 1265, 1140, 825, 755. (Found: S, 20.14. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_9\text{N}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}$, S, 20.58%). IV(R = H₃CO-C₆H₄), m.p. $>290^\circ$, (Found: S, 19.95. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{11}\text{N}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}$, S, 19.69%).

Thiazolo [4,5-b] quinoxaline V(R = H) :

It was synthesized by reacting equimolecular proportions of I and thioamides in presence of anhydrous sodium acetate in ethanol in the manner described above m.p. $>280^\circ$, $\nu_{\max}$ (cm^{-1}) 3100, 1610, 1485, 1330, 1160, 755. (Found: S, 16.68. Calcd. for $\text{C}_9\text{H}_8\text{N}_2\text{S}$, S, 17.11%). Similarly were prepared V(R = CH₃), m.p. $>290^\circ$ (Found: S, 16.33. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_7\text{N}_2\text{S}$, S, 15.92%), V(R = C₆H₅), m.p. $>290^\circ$ (Found: S, 11.87. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_9\text{N}_2\text{S}$, S, 12.16%). V(R = m-NO₂-C₆H₄), m.p. $>290^\circ$ (Found: S, 9.86. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_8\text{N}_2\text{SO}_2$, S, 10.39%).

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Synthesis of O, O-Dialkyl-S-[3-(Aryloxymethyl)-4-Substituted Phenyl-1,2,4-Triazol-5-yl]-Dithiophosphate as Possible Acetylcholinesterase (AChE) Inhibitors and Bactericides

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ORGANOPHOSPHATES have been extensively used as insecticides^{1,2} and exhibit antiacetylcholinesterase activities^{3,4}. A number of substituted triazoles are good bactericides^{5,6}, fungicides⁷⁻⁹ and herbicides^{10,11}. Triazoles with phenoxy methyl moiety are expected to have increased pesticidal activities as phenoxy acetic acid itself has been associated with various biological activities^{12,13}. In the present communication we have condensed several substituted triazoles with O,O-dialkyl chlorothiophosphate in order to synthesise O,O-dialkyl-S-[3-(aryloxymethyl)-4-substituted phenyl-1,2,4-triazol-5-yl]-dithiophosphates (I, Table 1) and tested for their biological activities.

Experimental

Melting points were taken in open capillaries and are uncorrected. The synthesised compounds have been characterised by ir spectroscopy and elemental analysis.

O, O-Dialkylchlorothiophosphate was prepared by known method of Fletcher *et al*¹⁴. Thiophosphoryl chloride was prepared according to the method of Moellar¹⁵. The key intermediate substituted triazoles have been prepared by known procedure¹⁶.

O, O-Dialkyl-S-[3-(4-Chlorophenoxyethyl)-4-Phenyl-1,2,4-triazol-5-yl]-dithiophosphate :

O,O-Dialkylchlorothiophosphate (0.01 M) and 3-(4-chlorophenoxyethyl)-5-mercapto-4-phenyl-1,2,4-triazole (0.01 M) was refluxed in dry acetone

TABLE 1. PHYSICAL DATA AND ANTIBACTERIAL ACTIVITY OF O,O-DIALKYL S-[3-(ARYLOXYMETHYL)-4-SUBSTITUTED PHENYL-1,2,4-TRIAZOL-5-YL]-DITHIOPHOSPHATES

Sl. No.	R ₁	R ₂	R ₃	R	m.p. °C	Molecular Formula	Bactericidal Activity		
							<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>B. pumilus</i>	<i>B. subtilis</i>
1.	H	Cl	Ph	Me	113	C ₁₇ H ₁₇ ClN ₃ O ₂ PS ₂	++	-	++
2.	H	Cl	Ph	Et	92	C ₁₉ H ₂₁ ClN ₃ O ₂ PS ₂	+	++	-
3.	H	Cl	Ph	Pr	115	C ₂₁ H ₂₅ ClN ₃ O ₂ PS ₂	-	-	-
4.	H	Cl	Ph	Bu	118	C ₂₃ H ₂₉ ClN ₃ O ₂ PS ₂	+	-	-
5.	H	Me	Ph	Me	100	C ₁₈ H ₂₀ N ₃ O ₂ PS ₂	+	++	-
6.	H	Me	Ph	Et	95	C ₂₀ H ₂₄ N ₃ O ₂ PS ₂	+	++	+
7.	H	Me	Ph	Pr	85	C ₂₂ H ₂₈ N ₃ O ₂ PS ₂	-	++	-
8.	H	Me	Ph	Bu	98	C ₂₄ H ₃₂ N ₃ O ₂ PS ₂	-	++	-
9.	Me	H	Ph	Me	90	C ₁₈ H ₂₀ N ₃ O ₂ PS ₂	+	++	+
10.	Me	H	Ph	Et	98	C ₂₀ H ₂₄ N ₃ O ₂ PS ₂	+	-	-
11.	Me	H	Ph	Pr	169	C ₂₂ H ₂₈ N ₃ O ₂ PS ₂	-	++	-
12.	Me	H	Ph	Bu	105	C ₂₄ H ₃₂ N ₃ O ₂ PS ₂	-	++	-
13.	H	Me	4-MeC ₆ H ₄	Me	113	C ₁₉ H ₂₁ N ₃ O ₂ PS ₂	++	++	++
14.	H	Me	1-MeC ₆ H ₄	Pr	168	C ₂₁ H ₂₅ N ₃ O ₂ PS ₂	-	++	-
15.	H	Me	4-MeC ₆ H ₄	Bu	87	C ₂₃ H ₂₉ N ₃ O ₂ PS ₂	-	-	-
16.	H	Cl	4-MeC ₆ H ₄	Me	146	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ ClN ₃ O ₂ PS ₂	-	++	-
17.	H	Cl	4-MeC ₆ H ₄	Et	188	C ₂₁ H ₂₁ ClN ₃ O ₂ PS ₂	-	+	++
18.	H	Cl	4-MeC ₆ H ₄	Pr	196	C ₂₃ H ₂₅ ClN ₃ O ₂ PS ₂	-	-	-
19.	H	Cl	1-MeC ₆ H ₄	Bu	199	C ₂₅ H ₂₉ ClN ₃ O ₂ PS ₂	-	-	-
20.	Me	H	4-MeC ₆ H ₄	Me	91	C ₁₉ H ₂₁ N ₃ O ₂ PS ₂	++	+++	++
21.	Me	H	1-MeC ₆ H ₄	Et	99	C ₂₁ H ₂₅ N ₃ O ₂ PS ₂	+	++	++

1. Elemental analysis results were within ±0.4% of the calculated values.
2. All the compounds were obtained in 40-60% yield.
3. For antibacterial screening: - = no inhibition; + = 6-8 mm inhibition, ++ = 9-5 mm inhibition, +++ = 16-20 mm inhibition.

in presence of anhydrous K₂CO₃ for several hours. The mixture was filtered and concentrated and the solid thus obtained was crystallised from suitable solvent (Table 1).

Biological Data :

Determination of Antibacterial Activity :

The newly synthesised organophosphorous compounds were evaluated for their bactericidal activity against *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Bacillus pumilus* and *Bacillus subtilis* using agar plate diffusion technique¹⁷. The average inhibition by various compounds has been recorded in Table 1. The results indicate that all the organophosphorous compounds are marginal antibacterial in nature.

Antiacetylcholinesterase Activity :

The enzyme activity was assayed essentially according to the method proposed by Diggle *et al*¹⁸ which is a modification of Hestrin's¹⁹ method. The compounds were dissolved in propylene glycol and used at a concentration of 7.4 × 10⁻⁵. A control containing equal volume of propylene glycol was also run in parallel. The inhibition obtained has been recorded in Table 2 along with the I₅₀ values of the organophosphates which indicate the concentration required to produce 50% enzyme inhibition.

TABLE 2—ANTIACETYLCHOLINESTERASE ACTIVITY

Sl. No.	R ₁	R ₂	R ₃	R	Conc.	used	%Inhibition	I ₅₀ × 10 ⁻⁵ M
1.	H	Cl	Ph	Me	7.4 × 10 ⁻⁵	36.4	10.164	
2.	H	Cl	Ph	Pr	7.4 × 10 ⁻⁵	25.0	13.800	
3.	H	Me	Ph	Et	7.4 × 10 ⁻⁵	18.2	20.329	
4.	Me	H	Ph	Me	7.4 × 10 ⁻⁵	9.1	40.659	
5.	Me	H	Ph	Pr	7.4 × 10 ⁻⁵	9.1	40.659	
6.	H	Me	4-MeC ₆ H ₄	Me	7.4 × 10 ⁻⁵	13.7	27.007	
7.	H	Me	4-MeC ₆ H ₄	Bu	7.4 × 10 ⁻⁵	13.7	27.007	
8.	H	Cl	4-MeC ₆ H ₄	Me	7.4 × 10 ⁻⁵	35.0	10.571	
9.	H	Cl	4-MeC ₆ H ₄	Pr	7.4 × 10 ⁻⁵	22.8	16.228	
10.	Me	H	4-MeC ₆ H ₄	Et	7.4 × 10 ⁻⁵	18.2	20.329	

I₅₀ value for Neostigmine, a potent antiacetylcholinesterase inhibitor used as standard in the similar conditions is 1.96 × 10⁻⁷.

Results and Discussion

The acetylcholinesterase activity of O,O-Dialkyl-S-[3-(aryloxymethyl)4-substituted phenyl-1,2,4-triazol-5-yl] dithiophosphates and their I₅₀ values are shown in Table 2.

All the compounds exhibit marginal activity except few. The compounds substituted with chloro group in the phenyl ring are better inhibitor of the enzyme. Compound 4 and 5 substituted with methyl group at 3-position are devoid of enzyme inhibitory action. Presence of a methyl group at 4-position did not alter their ability to inhibit acetylcholinesterase. It is seen that as the length of alkyl

chain in phosphorous moiety increases, enzyme inhibition decreases. Compounds having propyl substitution at 'R' are better inhibitors as compared to the ethyl substituted in the phosphorous side chain. Thus in the phosphorous side chain, the order of inhibitory action against acetylcholinesterase is Me > Pr > Et > Bu.

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4-NN-Bis-2'-Carboxyethylaminobenzaldehyde as Spray Reagent for Acyl Glycines in Paper Chromatography

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FORMATION of highly coloured azlactones prompted the use of aromatic aldehydes as reagent for acyl glycines¹⁻³. The present note reports the synthesis of 4-NN-bis-2'-carboxyethylaminobenzaldehyde (*bis*-CEAB) which on condensation with acyl glycines gave deep coloured 2-substituted phenyl-4-(4'-NN-bis-β-carboxyethylaminobenzylidene)-5-oxazolones(I).

Data concerning the new products are set out in the Table I.

The use of *bis*-CEAB as spray reagent for acyl glycines has been explored. The sensitivity of *bis*-CEAB is good and the colour produced are generally intense and stable.

Experimental

Synthesis of acyl glycines⁴⁻⁶ and of oxazolones (I)¹⁻³ was accomplished as reported in literature. Uncorrected m.p.s. are reported.

4-NN-Bis-2'-carboxyethylaminobenzaldehyde (*bis*-CEAB) :

4-NN-Bis-2'-cyanoethylaminobenzaldehyde⁷ (10.0 g) and aq. sodium hydroxide (100 ml, 10%) was refluxed for one hr. and the solution was neutralised with conc. sulphuric acid (9.4 ml, density 1.84) when *bis*-CEAB precipitated. It was filtered under suction and recrystallised from water; m.p. 141; yield, 8.2 g. (70.7%). Found: C, 58.3; H, 5.98; N, 5.56; C₁₈H₁₅O₅N requires C, 58.8; H, 5.66 and N, 5.28% IR(KBr) shows peaks at 1730 and 1690 cm⁻¹ (C=O) and at 1320 cm⁻¹ (tert. amino gr.). 2:4-Dinitrophenyl hydrazone prepared by usual methods, m.p. 210°.

One per cent solution of *bis*-CEAB in acetic anhydride and fused sodium acetate was found